

NOTES

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Study of Nickel(II) Complex with Potassium Butyl Xanthate

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POTASSIUM butyl xanthate was prepared and purified in the laboratory¹. A stock solution of nickel sulphate was prepared in distilled water and standardised gravimetrically². Buffer solutions were prepared by standard procedures HCl-KCl (pH 1-2); acetic acid-sodium acetate (3-6); KH_2PO_4 -NaOH (6-8); borax-NaOH (9-10). Beckman DU-2 model spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cell was used for absorption measurements. A pH meter (ECIL, India) was used for pH measurements. The infrared spectra were recorded as KBr pellets in Beckman Infrared spectrophotometer 20.

Procedure :

An aliquot (2 ml) of the suitably diluted stock solution containing 252 μg of Ni was mixed with 8 ml of buffer solution of desired pH. Foreign ions were added to the nickel solution before addition of the buffer to test their interferences. The volume of the aqueous phase was maintained at 10 ml throughout the work. Aqueous potassium butyl xanthate (1 ml, 0.5%) was added and the mixture was kept for 10 minutes to ensure complete complexation. Nickel(II) forms a yellow-brown chelate. It was extracted with 10 ml chloroform in a separating funnel for 2 minutes followed by washing of the aqueous phase with 2×5 ml chloroform to avoid loss. The organic layer was transferred, dried and diluted to 25 ml with chloroform and its absorbance was measured at 415 nm against a reagent blank and the nickel extracted was determined from a previously prepared calibration curve.

All the experiments were carried out at 26-27°.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Curve, Effect of pH reagent Concentration and Stability of Colour :

The spectrum of Ni(II) butyl xanthate in chloroform shows two absorption maxima at 415 nm and 475 nm. The molar absorptivity of the complex corresponding to these wavelengths were 3.2×10^3 and 1.8×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ respectively and

sensitivity in terms of Sandell's definition is 0.018 g. Hence, all measurements were made at 415 nm. Colour of the complex is stable at least for 48 hours. The extraction behaviour was studied over the pH range 1-11. The extraction is quantitative at pH 5-7. Anions of buffers do not interfere in the estimation. Nickel is quantitatively extracted into chloroform in a single operation when the layers are shaken for 2 minutes. Other variables remaining the same, 1 ml of 0.5% aqueous solutions of the reagent is sufficient to extract 252 μg of Ni. Reagent concentration below of 0.4% results in incomplete extraction.

Diverse ions : Diverse ions were examined to test their interferences on extraction at pH 5. The following ions may be tolerated when present in amounts (μg) shown in parenthesis : Be(II) (3500), Mg(II) (4800), La(III) (3500), Cr(III) (3000), Mn(II) (1500), Fe(III) (2200), Co(III) (2500), Rh(II) (1000), Zn(II) (4000), Al(III) (4000), Ce(III) (2500), U(VI) (3000), Th(IV) (3000), W(VI) (4000), V(V) (4000), fluoride (10000), thiocyanate (6000), phosphate (8000), bromide (8000), iodide (7000), thiosulphate (5000), acetate (1000), borate (8000), citrate (8000), oxalate (9000), tartrate (8000), phthalate (10000).

Nickel is incompletely extracted in presence of Zr(IV), Os(VIII), Cu(II), Hg(II), Cd(II), Pb(II) and Bi(III), Ru(III), Pd(II) and Pt(IV) which are co-extracted and give high results. Attempts to mask these ions failed. Fe(III) was masked by ammonium hydrogen fluoride to check its co-extraction. Interference of Co(III) was removed by a preliminary extraction as the thiocyanate complex into amyl alcohol.

In the complex Ni is combined with xanthate in the ratio of 1 : 2 as determined by the method of continuous variation and mole ratio method. The stability constant is found to be 3.703×10^9 and the standard free energy of formation of the complex is -13.2 KCal/mole at 27°.

The Infrared Spectrum : The bands of the complex at 1460, 1450, 1440 and 1380 cm⁻¹ are due to methylene bending deformation and asymmetrical methyl deformation mode. The absorption frequency at 1400 cm⁻¹, absent in the case of ethyl xanthate, may be attributed to perturbed methylene group. The absorption bands at 1275 and 1260 cm⁻¹ were absent in the reagent and as such, believed to have been formed due to complex formation. Little and Poling^{3,4} have shown that for complexes with xanthate type of compounds, bands around 1275 and 1260 cm⁻¹ had negative $\Delta\nu$ and cannot be assigned to C=S stretching mode. In the

region 1020-1070 cm^{-1} , $\Delta\nu$ for the complex were 0 to +9 cm^{-1} and confirmed the C=S assignment of the bands. As the C-O-C frequencies of the complex are expected to be higher than the alkali xanthate, the absorption frequencies of the complex at 1275 and 1260 cm^{-1} may be attributed to C-O-C linkage.

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Chemical Constituents of the Flowers of *Strobilanthes callosus* (Acanthaceae)

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STROBILANTHES callosus Nees, is a herb having yellowish flowers with spikes and panicles. In India plant is commonly known as Karvi. Flowers and leaves are used for different purposes¹⁻². No chemical studies have so far been reported on this plant.

Air dried flowers were extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was divided into acidic and neutral fraction by usual method. The neutral fraction on column chromatography over neutral alumina gave four different substances marked A, B, C, and D.

The GLC analysis of the substance A m.p. 62-67° over 3% SE 30 column at 250° showed it to be a mixture of n-alkanes containing hentriacontane (36.3%), tritriacontane (28.9%), nonacosane (21.2%), dotriacontane (4.5%) and triacontane (2.9%), heptacosane (2.0%), hexatriacontane (1.5%), tetratriacontane (1.0%), octacosane (1.0%) accompanied by hexacosane, pentacosane, and pentatriacontane as a minor constituent. Fraction B m.p. 79-80° was classified as saturated alcohol by I.R.

and Co-TLC. GLC analysis showed it to be a mixture of n-alcohols containing tetratriacontanol (40.5%), dotriacontanol (30.5%), tritriacontanol (20.8%), triacontanol (4.3%), hentriacontanol (3.6%). Nonacosanol, pentatriacontanol, and hexatriacontanol was also found as a trace constituent.

The compound C m.p. 210° gave positive Liebermann Burchard and Noller's test. I.R., m.p., m.m.p. and Co-TLC showed it to be lupeol. Compound D m.p. was identified as sterol by Liebermann Burchard and Noller's test. GC-MS analysis³ showed it to be a mixture of four sterols. Cholesterol (0.4%) (M^+ 458), campesterol (11.0%) (M^+ 472), stigmasterol (41.5%) (M^+ 484) and β -sitosterol (47.0%) (M^+ 486).

The acidic fraction contains mainly saturated fatty acids m.p. 65°. GLC analysis at 250° showed it to be a mixture of C_{24} - C_{30} fatty acids; pentacosanoic acid (54.0%), heptacosanoic acid (22.5%), nonacosanoic acid (8.5%), hexacosanoic acid (6.2%), octacosanoic acid (3.5%), pentatriacontanoic acid (2.6%) and hentriacontanoic acid (2.3%) along with the minor quantities of triacontanoic acid and heptatriacontanoic acid.

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Base Adducts of Bis (Acetylacetonato) Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donors

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LEWIS acid behaviour of metal chelates of β -diketones and related compounds which involve keto-enol tautomerism have invoked lot of interest in recent years. Stability of β -diketonates has been partly explained on the basis of benzenoid resonance¹ and reactions characteristic of aromatic system have been carried out²⁻⁴ on metal β -diketonates to provide further evidence regarding the aromaticity. We have been trying for the adduct formation of metal β -diketonates with heterocyclic bases and isolated a number adducts of Zinc(II)⁵⁻⁷ and Copper(II)^{8,9} β -diketonates with